

Resonant states in 2D disordered photonic band gap structures

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Abstract: During the last decades, 2D-ordered and disordered photonic systems have attracted intense attention as systems capable to control and modify the flow of light. These structures can also localize the light into the band gap by exciting states arising from cavities, defects, or photonic molecules. We report a controllable random disordered photonic system of silicon dielectric cylinders that presents a deep band gap and, superimposed, two tunable resonant states generated from decagonal ring resonators embedded into it. These states show a high transmission intensity and a bandwidth that remains stable when its geometrical parameters for frequency tuning are modified. The ability to tune the resonating frequencies with the geometrical parameters of the system allows interesting applications such as sensing and filtering.

1. Introduction

There are many photonic systems that, conveniently tailored, provide interesting applications such as sensing, filtering, etc. One of these platforms is based on the existence of a bandgap and some controllable states inside the gap. Both phenomena, the bandgap, and resonant states appear together for instance in quasicrystals based on Penrose tiling¹⁻³ or in defects induced in hyperuniform lattices⁴. However, understanding the role of each part of the structure allows a much more flexible design, easily tailored for particular applications.

It is well established that, in nonperiodic arrangements of cylinders, their Mie scattering is sufficient to generate band gaps. These arrangements can be periodic or quasiperiodic⁵, disordered hyperuniform arrangements⁶, or completely random, although limiting the maximum proximity of cylinders⁷. These band gaps are clearly present in TM polarization while for TE only in some hyperuniform distributions an appreciable effect has been reported⁶.

In this paper, we study a photonic platform built with (i) collective resonators, that produce the states and (ii) a randomly disordered background that provides the band gap. With a suitable geometrical design of the structure geometry, we can have independent control of the main optical parameters of the system: bandgap and frequency values of resonant states and their transmission properties (mainly contrast between gap and states).

The structure of the following sections was chosen to emphasize the idea of the independence of the two structures, each providing one of the desired optical properties. So, after presenting the calculation procedures, the results section is divided into three subsections, one for the bandgap produced by a random distribution of cylinders, the second for the resonators and the states generated and finally we show that the geometrical addition of both substructures produces the superposition of their optical characteristics. To conclude, we discuss some possible applications of this kind of platform.

2. Calculation procedure

The results presented in this work are based on numerical simulations. Although no experimental results are included in this case, our group has checked the reliability of this calculation procedure by testing it against actual measurements, in the microwave region, of physical structures built of glass cylinders of several millimeters in diameter^{8,9}. Since the Maxwell equations governing the studied system exhibit scale invariance, the findings in the microwave regime can be easily extended to the optical range. This extrapolation involves scaling the size of materials and the wavelength by the same factor. Consequently, it is important to consider the dielectric permittivity in both the microwave and optical ranges, particularly its imaginary part that represents material losses. Although such losses can often be disregarded in the microwave range, they must be considered in optics¹⁰.

Numerical calculations were carried out with CST MICROWAVE STUDIO™, a commercial code based on the Finite Integration time-domain Method (FIM) ¹¹. Transmission and Scattering Cross Section (SCS) simulations use the Frequency Domain Solver tool, using tetrahedral adaptive mesh refinement. In this work, we consider the transverse magnetic (TM) polarization of the incident radiation, with the electric field vector parallel to the cylinder's axis. Transverse electric (TE) polarization is not considered because it does not generate a band gap in the transmittance spectrum (see Fig. S1 in Supplement 1 for supporting content). In order to perform transmission calculations, a unit cell is repeated indefinitely in the x and y -axis by applying periodical boundary conditions. Transmittance and reflectance spectra are calculated from a summation of the power density in all diffraction orders excited by the lattice. As the dielectric permittivity employed for the calculations is real, absorptivity is not considered in the power balance. The photonic transmission calculations are performed on samples of finite dimensions in the direction of light transmission. In this work, we have selected the permittivity of silicon ($\epsilon = 12$), a material suitable for building actual photonic structures. SCS was numerically calculated by the ratio of scattered power density to the incident power density over the surface of a cylinder with radius r ¹².

Frequency values are presented normalized to the cylinder size resulting in dimensionless units. In this way results are directly applicable to any actual range due to scalability of the Maxwell Equation.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, we present the results of the construction of a photonic device by the superposition of two substructures. In order to make it clear, we present separately the design and optical performance of each substructure and afterward the complete system that merges the former.

3.1 Random distributions of cylinders

A randomly disordered distribution of cylinders can produce a significant photonic gap. In order to assess the statistical characteristics of different arrangements, we start with very large samples. However, as we see later, much smaller arrays are enough to have the desired gap.

Here, we consider bidimensional samples (2D) in which we place N cylinders of radius r arranged in either a random or an ordered triangular configuration. The cylinders are contained in a square box of size L , and have a density of $\rho = N/L^2$. We can define a length scale factor a to normalize the distances between the cylinder as $a = L/\sqrt{N}$ with results in a filling factor of $ff = \rho\pi r^2 = \pi(r/a)^2$. The disorder of the random lattices is controlled by the k factor, defined as the minimum center-to-center distance between the disordered cylinders in the box⁷. The k -factor produces an *exclusion zone* around each cylinder. By definition, the value of k must be greater or equal to 0 to avoid cylinders overlapping. The abovementioned minimum distance is defined considering the radius of the cylinder but scaled by the k -factor as in the equation,

$$d_{\min} = 2r \times (1 + k) \quad (1)$$

A pseudo-random distribution (Matlab function *rand*) is used to generate the coordinates (x,y) of each cylinder in the lattice. When placing a new cylinder, its distance to all previous ones has to be checked to assure that none is below d_{\min} . If it is the case, the coordinates are discarded and a new iteration begins. The process is repeated until the desired number of cylinders (N) is reached. The complexity of the process depends on the ff and the k -factor. We have studied a range of k values from 1 to 1.6 because a greater value makes the calculation time extremely long.

Fig. 1 presents a scheme of the samples analyzed. Four samples with different degrees of disorder were designed. The red box shows a detail area (width w and height h) for a periodic triangular lattice (Fig.1(a)), and random lattices of $k=0.5$ (Fig.1(b)), $k=0.25$ (Fig.1(c)) and $k=0$ (Fig.1(d)), respectively. All samples have similar ff and N with a value of 0.23 and 8135, respectively. The size of L is $90.2a$ and the ratio between length scale and cylinder radius r/a 0.27.

Fig. 1. Four lattices generated. The upper figure indicates the size used to assess their statistical features. The lower ones, at the size adequate for photonic calculations, correspond to (a) periodic triangular, and the rest are random lattices with (b) $k=0.5$, (c) $k=0.25$, and (d) $k=0$.

The degree of disorder for the proposed structures is characterized by using $\sigma^2(R)$, which is the variance of $N(R)$, the distribution of the number of particles in a region defined by a circle $\Omega(R)$ of radius constant R but variable number of centers ⁶, and is given by

$$\sigma^2 = \langle N(R^2) \rangle - \langle N(R) \rangle^2 \quad (2)$$

In Fig.2, we plot number variance $\sigma^2(R)$ versus R/a for the ordered triangular lattice and the random arrays. Fit curves of the form $\sigma^2(R)=AR^2$ are presented together with the number variance data ¹³. In the random lattices of cylinders, $\sigma^2(R)$ grows as the d -dimensional region of radius R , $\sigma^2(R) \sim R^2$, but is weighted by the k -factor applied in every case. In terms of disorder, the number variance of the distribution of cylinders grows slowly as the k factor increases since the structure is more homogenous and the clustering phenomena related to short distances are canceled, as is shown in Fig 1. On the other hand, the triangular lattice presents oscillating $\sigma^2(R)$ with R due to the high number of fluctuations of $N(R)$ near the circle window boundary of $\Omega(R)$ and number variance tends to grow up with R^2 as can be seen in Fig. 2⁶.

Fig. 2. The number variance σ^2 vs region radius R for the samples presented in Fig. 1. Red triangles: disordered random array $k=0$, with the blue long-dashed line indicating a fit to $\sigma^2 \propto R^2$; green squares: disordered random array $k=0.25$, with the brown dot-dashed line indicating a fit to $\sigma^2 \propto R^2$; yellow diamonds: disordered random array $k=0$, with the red medium-dashed line indicating a fit to $\sigma^2 \propto R^2$; black circles: triangular ordered array, with the green short-dashed line indicating a fit to $\sigma^2 \propto R^2$.

Once studied the disorder of the designed random arrays, we calculate their electromagnetic behavior and capability to create a photonic band gap. Firstly, we have to calculate the transmission of the disordered samples, where the sample width (w) is crucial. The size of the sample limits the transmitted power. For that reason, we have analyzed a reduced version of the lattice shown in Fig. 1(b), 1(c), and 1(d). We choose a value for w of $15.7a$ to obtain a significant band gap contrast. The height value h corresponds to $11.3a$. In order to analyze the role of sample size w , we have simulated different widths for the sample of $k=0.5$ (Fig. 1(b)). The spectra were calculated starting with the whole array. At each iteration, cylinders were removed row after row on both sides by width steps of $1/9w$ [8]. The result is shown in figure 3. The width of every step \hat{w} is depicted normalized to w in the horizontal axis, normalized frequency in the vertical one, and the transmission is represented through a jet colormap in the third dimension. A deep bandgap between 0.13 and 0.18 is created by the random array from \hat{w} of 0.35. In terms of depth, the bandgap reaches around -50 dB at 0.35 and a deep value of -120 dB near 1. This result assures that the width selected is adequate to generate a significant bandgap response.

Fig. 3. Color map plots of calculated transmission spectra for a random disordered lattice of k -value 0.5 as a function of normalized width (\hat{w}) in the direction of transmission and normalized frequency ($2r/\lambda$).

Figure 4 shows the transmittance spectra of samples with the same width ($\hat{w} = 1$, or equivalently $w = 15.9a$) but different k -factor values, the same cases presented in figures 1 and 2. In all cases presented, a significant gap exists. However, for $k = 0$, several peaks appear, making the gap edges less steep. This behavior arises from the random appearance of resonating cavities due to the statistical clustering of the cylinders. As the k -factor increases, this clustering is avoided, and the band gap becomes broader, deeper, and free of spurious states.

Fig. 4. Calculated transmission spectra of randomly disordered lattices of cylinders with k -values of 0 (black dashed line), 0.25 (red dot-dashed line), and 0.5 (blue solid line), respectively. The height and width values of the samples correspond to $11.3a$ and $15.2a$, respectively. The filling factor is 0.23 in all cases.

2.3 Collective resonators

In this paper we present a photonic structure that operates as the superposition of two structures, the random background and individual resonators. In this section, we described the resonators used.

Many dielectric structures resonate with incident electromagnetic radiation at particular frequencies. Simple geometries such as spheres or cylinders resonate in a predictable way that can be solved analytically (Mie modes). More complex structures or even the absence of dielectric elements in the lattice (defects or vacancies) can also produce well-defined resonances^{14,15}. Out of this plethora of possibilities, we have chosen collective resonators, decagonal rings of cylinders in particular, due to the resonant performance shown previously.^{8,9} These rings resonator appear naturally in quasiperiodic arrays derived from Penrose tiling process. Depending on the symmetry of these tailings, the rings can contain different numbers of cylinders.

We have selected a decagonal ring made with the same cylinders (see Fig. 5(a)) as the disordered background. The rings are determined by the parameter τ (the distance between the center and border ring) and the cylinder radius r . In our case, the ratio r/τ is 0.25. The decagonal ring has n -fold rotational geometry of order $n=10$ since a rotation by an angle of $360^\circ/n$ does not change it. Therefore, the variation of the incident radiation angle φ is limited to the interval from 0° to 18° . Figure 5(b) presents the Scattering Cross Section (SCS) of one decagonal resonator of dielectric permittivity of 12 for two different incident radiation angles φ , 0° (incident radiation perpendicular to the ring) and 18° .

Both SCS spectra are almost identical but the state at 0.143 is excited at 18° and not for 0° . This fact was reported (and proposed as an incidence angle sensor) in previous works^{1,9}. In view of this behavior, we have selected for the rest of the paper an incident angle φ of 18° . The peaks of the SCS spectrum correspond to particular resonant modes geometries of the ring⁷. The selected resonator presents resonances at normalized frequency values of 0.06, 0.085, 0.112, 0.134, and 0.146. The first three resonances are not inside the band gap of the randomly disordered lattice (from 0.13 to 0.18), and only the last two states could be excited in the gap.

Fig.5 (a) Structure of decagonal ring resonator employed in this paper. The resonator is made of cylinders of radius r arranged as a ring in decagonal symmetry. Axis labeling and parameter definition of the design are labeled. (b) Scattering cross section of a decagonal ring of cylinders. Peaks correspond to particular resonance modes. Note that incident radiation with an angle of 18° excites a resonance that is missing at perpendicular 0° .

3.3 Combined system: resonators in a random background

The structure proposed is composed of the two sets of cylinders previously presented: (i) ring resonators and (ii) disordered background. A sample as a combination of both ones is presented in Figure 6 for the case of $k=0.5$. The decagonal rings used as resonators are shown in black in Fig. 6. The unit cell of the structure (red dashed-line in Fig. 6) is built with a rectangular array of 2×3 resonators embedded in the randomly placed cylinders. The distance between the decagonal rings of the array p , is $4.51a$, and the offset from the decagonal rings to the unit cell edge is $2.25a$. Width (w), height (h), and the rest of the parameters of the decagonal rings have already been indicated in subsections 3.1 and 3.2.

Fig. 6. (a) Diagram of the combined structure proposed in this paper. h and w correspond to the height and width of the unit cell. Radiation propagates in the z -direction. The structure is composed of a 3×2 array of decagonal rings separated by a distance p and depicted by a green dashed box. Randomly placed cylinders surrounding the rings are colored blue. The filling factor is 0.23 and the k -factor is 0.5

Previously, we analyzed each structure separately. Now, we check the combined lattice and evaluate the degree of influence on each other. In Fig. 7, we plot together three sets of data: (i) the transmission spectrum of a random lattice (corresponding to Fig 1. (d)), (ii) the SCS of the decagonal ring, and (iii) the transmittance of the complete sample shown in Fig. 6. We also show the electric field intensity distribution of the modes inside the gap as identified in the SCS and transmittance calculations (labeled 1 and 2). The field data are presented normalized to ± 1 (red and blue) in all cases.

Figure 7. Effect of substructures superposition. (a) Transmittance of a random sample with $k=0.5$. (b) Scattering cross section of a decagonal ring. (c) Transmittance of the sample that includes a random background and six resonators. To ease comparisons, all figures are referred to the same x -axis and present an inset of the simulated structure (bottom right). Inserts in (b) and (c) show the electric field distribution of the resonators for the frequencies of the peaks labeled 1 and 2.

As the three plots are referred to the same normalized frequency axis ($2r/\lambda$), it is easy to recognize in the lower image the features of the others. The field distributions around the resonator rings also assure that the resonances inside the random background are the same as the ones excited in the isolated resonator. It is interesting to note that the excited states (labeled by 1 and 2) in the complete structure are wider than the SCS ones; also present some structure, as if they were composed of different resonances. This is the case; small variations of the frequency show different field distributions with the same symmetry in the rings (the one shown in the figures) but with different intensities in the array of six resonators (see Fig. S3 in Supplement 1 for supporting content). However, as will be discussed in figure 9, these small variations of the resonances respond in the same way to changes in the geometrical parameters of the rings.

As shown in Figure 7, both the disordered cylinder structure and the 3x2 array of decagonal rings, exhibit a deep and sharp bandgap. As previously noted, this bandgap is highly dependent on polarization and can only be excited by an electric field parallel to the lattice cylinders. However, the bandgap of the disordered cylinders is independent of the incidence angle in the transverse plane (yz plane), demonstrating omnidirectional behavior due to an omnidirectional photonic bandgap (PBG). When the array of decagonal rings is added to the structure (Fig. 7(c)), the band gap does not undergo relevant changes and remains present but includes the states excited by the decagonal rings array. For more details on the lack of angle variation please refer to Figure S5 in Supplement 1.

We have also analyzed, as in figure 4, the influence of disorder degree induced by the k -factor in the optical transmission of the complete system. We have calculated the transmittance of a set of 12 structures with the same six-ring resonators of figure 6, but with backgrounds of different k -factors, ranging from 0.01 to 0.6. The result of these calculations is presented in Fig. 8, a 3D color map where transmission spectra are piled up z -axis for the different k -factors. A linear interpolation function was employed to improve the image. The transmission value is depicted in a jet color scale to ease visualization. Here also, the frequency values are presented normalized to cylinder diameter ($2r/\lambda$), resulting in a dimensionless magnitude.

Fig. 8. Color map plots of simulated transmission spectra against k -factor and normalized frequency. The vertical axis depicts frequency, while the transmission value is color-coded (red for full transmission, and blue for -80 dB). Frequency is presented normalized to the diameter of the cylinders ($2r$).

As it can be seen, for values of k greater than 0.3, there is a clearly well-defined gap with values of transmission less than -80 dB. However, as k -factor decreases, the bandgap edges become closer and noisier. In all cases, the resonator states are present at the same frequencies (around 0.137 and 0.147). These values correspond to the expected decagonal ring eigenstates as was previously analyzed and shown^{2,9}.

Finally, we want to introduce the possibility of tuning the states in the gap. These photonic states are due to the resonances of the decagonal rings of cylinders, and the resonances are very dependent on the resonator geometry. They also depend on the cylinder dielectric permittivity, but in this work, for the sake of simplicity, we are not considering variations in this parameter. In order to discuss this behavior, some calculations were made for the disordered structure shown in Fig. 6. Transmission spectra were calculated by varying the parameter z of the decagonal ring but maintaining the radius constant. The results are presented in Fig. 9. The

calculated band gap response does not suffer significant changes regarding bandwidth and depth as the r/τ ratio increases. However, inside the band gap, we can observe how the excited states shift to a higher frequency as the r/τ increases.

Fig. 9. States tuning. Transmission spectra of rings with different geometries in the same disordered lattice with k -factor 0.5, filling factor 0.23. Decagonal rings tested are r/τ ratio of 0.25 (black solid line), 0.272 (red dashed line), and 0.285 (blue dash-dotted line).

We have presented a simple way of changing the frequency of the resonant state by modifying their proximity. However, there are other possibilities to change their resonant frequency such as varying cylinder characteristics (radius or dielectric permittivity) or the ring geometry.

This capacity of tuning the resonant frequencies by physical alterations of the structure is ideal for many applications such as tunable filters or sensors. We have previously presented examples of this kind of differential sensors for deformation¹⁶, incident radiation angle⁹, or dielectric permittivity¹⁷, but many others can be envisaged. In fact, the existence of different resonances can be used to design one that varies with the external parameter to be sensed and other at fixed, used as a reference. For these applications, the stability of the electromagnetic response against cylinder variations induced by fabrication tolerances is significant. We have tested the stability of the studied system (see Supplementary material for details) finding no output changes for cylinder radius variations up to $\pm 5\%$, which can be considered a good stability.

4. Conclusion

We have presented a 2D photonic platform made of cylinders with $\epsilon=12$ that presents tunable states inside a robust bandgap. The two main characteristics of this platform are designed independently, and the overall behavior arises from their superposition. One is the bandgap, obtained with a random distribution of cylinders

placed with a certain exclusion zone to avoid excessive clustering. The other is a decagonal ring of cylinders that presents very precise resonances. We have shown that placing ring resonators in a disordered background produces a system that keeps the optical performance of both subsystems. The capacity to tune the resonating frequencies with the geometrical parameters of the system allows interesting applications such as sensing and filtering.

Disclosures. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors under request.

Supplemental document. See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

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